
Authors and readers (of the constitution)

The problem of intention in legal interpretation

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“Man is an interpreting machine.” (Laurent Binet, *The Seventh Function of Language*)

“All those who followed in his footsteps had tried to unravel the mystery of the man... I remained focused on the mystery of the work.”
(Mohamed Mbougar Sarr, *The Most Secret Memory of Men*)¹

1 Introduction

- 1 Lawyers and judges often refer, in different ways, to what they call the “intention of the (constituent) legislator”.² Some constitutions even expressly identify the “will of the constituent legislator” as the object to which the interpretation should be directed.³ At the same time, theoretical and doctrinal discussions frequently invoke other “intentions” or “wills.” Thus, it is said that judges, as interpreters of normative texts, engage in an activity with an inevitable volitional component.⁴ Moreover, it is argued that texts themselves, independently of the “intentions” of their authors or interpreters, can plausibly express only a limited range of meanings – hence the idea of a “metaphorical intention of the text.”⁵
- 2 Against this background, this essay draws on a conceptual tool from semiotics to address some problems of legal interpretation. More specifically, it takes up a proposal developed by Umberto Eco in the context of general textual interpretation. Eco distinguishes three intentions: *intentio auctoris*, *intentio lectoris*, and *intentio operis*,⁶ which correspond to three different orientations or theories of interpretation (author-oriented, reader-oriented, and text-oriented).⁷ And although Eco is primarily

concerned with the interpretation of literary texts, this does not preclude some of these tools from being used for the analysis of legal interpretation, given what textual interpretation in general shares with legal interpretation in particular.⁸ The central point, it seems to me, is that this approach can be fruitful for examining, *for heuristic and explanatory purposes*, legal interpretation and the problem of the correctness of statements ascribing meaning.

- 3 This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 examines the “three intentions” and situates them within the broader debate on textual interpretation, first in general terms and then in relation to legal interpretation. Section 3 discusses the notion of authors and interpreters (of the constitution) in light of these three intentions, as well as the different accounts of interpretive error associated with them. Section 4 develops the analysis further by identifying some of the difficulties faced by each position, and then defends a view based on *intentio operis* under a specific form of moderate skepticism. In this respect – and subject to certain adjustments and qualifications – the paper argues in favor of the Gerundian version of moderate skepticism (associated with Jordi Ferrer Beltrán) over the Genoese position (associated with Riccardo Guastini), while also showing how the latter can, to some extent, be reconciled with the former. Finally, section 5 offers some qualifications.

2 Three intentions

- 4 As mentioned, Eco’s approach distinguishes “three intentions” in textual interpretation: *intentio auctoris*, *intentio lectoris*, and *intentio operis*. This framework also makes it possible to draw a comparison with some of the most widespread theories of legal interpretation. In their most radical versions, formalism and skepticism focus, respectively, on *intentio auctoris* and *intentio lectoris* (the former reducing law to the will of the legislator, the latter reducing it to the discourse of interpreters). By contrast, more recent theories, from normativism to moderate realism, adopt a (*lato sensu*) “textualist” approach to legal interpretation – one based on *intentio operis*.

2.1 *Intentio auctoris* and interpretation

- 5 In author-oriented interpretation (*intentio auctoris*), the aim of interpretation is understood to be the discovery of the author’s intention; that is, to grasp *what the author meant*. On this view, the interpreter must be able to speak on behalf of the author as if she were the author herself. Text T1 means M1 because the author intended it to mean precisely M1 (and not, for example, M2 or M3). Likewise, provision P1 expresses legal norm N1 because the legislator intended it to express N1 (and not N2, N3, or something else).⁹ This helps explain the old metaphor of the judge as the *bouche de la loi*, understood as the judge who does not speak – or should not speak – with his own voice, but must do so only with the “voice of the legislator.” On this approach, interpreting means faithfully applying the *will of the legislator*,¹⁰ whose understanding – by hypothesis – requires a certain form of communication.¹¹ “Laws,” it is said, are nothing more than intentionally legislative acts, and interpretation therefore consists in grasping the intention underlying such enactment.¹² In metaphorical terms, the interpreter becomes a kind of ventriloquist’s dummy who never speaks with his own voice (or, at least, should not do so).¹³

- 6 It might be thought that, in the legal context, this view refers only to an outdated, radical formalism, now largely superseded and almost forgotten (at least among legal philosophers¹⁴). However, this is not the case. Judges and jurists often continue to rely on assumptions of this kind, and some contemporary discussions have taken up these ideas again, albeit often under different labels.¹⁵ Consider, for instance, Ekins's account of constitutional interpretation:

The central object of constitutional interpretation is the Constitution, which is an intentional lawmaking act rather than a text floating free in the world, and ... the point of such interpretation is primarily to understand the meaning that those who made the Constitution intended to convey by promulgating the text in question.¹⁶

- 7 The author of a constitution is the *constituent* legislator or the ordinary legislator competent to exercise a reforming power (i.e., a *constituted* power¹⁷). Typically, however, it is not a *single* legislator but a *plurality* of legislators who participate in the drafting of a constitution or of particular constitutional provisions.¹⁸ The Italian Constitution, for example, is the result of a compromise among constituent legislators from different political camps: liberal, Christian-Democratic, and socialist. Even if it is granted – on this approach – that the precise content of a constitution is the product of *an* intention, it must still be acknowledged that this is not normally the intention of any *single* individual but is rather a putative *collective intention* (a hypothetically precise one, *à la* Ekins¹⁹).

2.2 *Intentio lectoris* and interpretation

- 8 In reader-oriented interpretation (*intentio lectoris*), the attribution of meaning is conceived, in a sense, as an activity that, from a textual point of view, is largely unconstrained: it is readers (interpreters) who freely attribute meaning to texts, beyond what – hypothetically – can be regarded as the *intentio auctoris*, whatever that may be, assuming it exists or can be determined. On this view – which, in the context of semiotic theory, is typical of deconstructionist approaches²⁰ – a text circulates “in the vacuum of a potentially infinite range of possible interpretations. As a consequence no text can be interpreted according to the utopia of a defined, original, and final authorized meaning.”²¹ In other words, interpretation would depend not on the author's intention but on the activity of the interpreters and their interpretive interests.²² On this position, therefore, no weak or robust criteria of correctness can be established in matters of interpretation: *anything goes*.²³
- 9 In the legal domain, the formalist approach identifies law with the normative texts that “contain” the intentions of the legislator – “the (intentional) discourse of the legislator.” By contrast, on the view at issue here, law is conceived as the meanings that interpreters intentionally attribute to those texts – “the (intentional) discourse of the interpreters.”²⁴ Normative texts are thus only *sources* of law, not *law* as such. This idea can already be found in the work of J.C. Gray²⁵ and can be summarized in a simple formula often associated with radical realism: *all law is judge-made law*. This amounts to a radical form of interpretive skepticism in which “all interpretation is creative of (a) meaning or (a) norm.”²⁶

2.3 *Intentio operis* and interpretation

- 10 In text-oriented interpretation (*intentio operis*), the text itself is taken to incorporate a (metaphorical) intention, hypothetically distinct from both the intention of the author and the intentions of its current or potential readers or interpreters. It may be the case – *ex hypothesi* – that the author of a text intends to communicate a certain message and yet that the same text supports meanings which were not intended by the author, or which are even contrary to the author’s intentions. Such meanings, it should be emphasized, are not thereby “objective,” nor are they necessarily intended to be so. Nevertheless, the *intentio operis* must also be distinguished from the *intentio lectoris*. The “author’s intention” and the (metaphorical) “intention of the text” are different things, and it is the latter that constitutes the standard of acceptable interpretations.²⁷ Accordingly, not all readings attributable to a text – potentially infinite – are admissible: readers can always offer their own interpretation, but not all of them will be equally correct.²⁸
- 11 Even if one were to grant – in certain cases and under certain criteria – that a text incorporates the intentions held by its author, this would not in *itself* determine the correctness of an interpretation. An author might have anticipated that a text would express one or more meanings determined by them (T1 expresses M1, and perhaps also M2, M3, and so on). Yet this does not confer on the author ultimate authority over the possible interpretations of the text. Readers may attribute further meanings, including creative ones. On Eco’s view, however, they remain constrained by the text (*intentio operis*), in the sense that the text itself limits the range of plausible meanings that can be accepted within an *interpretive community*.²⁹
- 12 In legal theory, approaches oriented toward *intentio operis* include the so-called mixed, eclectic, or *intermediate* theory of interpretation (as it is called by the Genoa School of Legal Philosophy³⁰), as well as what is usually referred to as *moderate realism* or *moderate skepticism*. The first position is both anti-formalist and anti-skeptical.³¹ The latter opposes formalism, radical skepticism, and the intermediate theory itself, although some authors – while remaining positioned within skepticism – have suggested that the distance between the intermediate theory and moderate skepticism is shorter than moderate skeptics themselves maintain. As Barberis puts it:
- [M]oderate interpretive skepticism differs, at least initially, from Hart’s mixed theory, although the difference depends on the weight each author attributes to doctrinal interpretation and judicial interpretation. Where doctrinal interpretation is privileged, moderate skepticism continues to be distinguished from mixed theory; when, on the other hand, the moment of judicial application is privileged, moderate skepticism and mixed theory tend to become confused.³²
- 13 Although there would be reasons to qualify Barberis’s claim, what matters here is that, with respect to judicial interpretation, both the intermediate theory and moderate skepticism are text-oriented approaches. In the intermediate theory, the text – and not the intention of the legislator – provides the standard in both clear and hard cases. *Open texture* is, of course, a property of language, discourse, and texts, not of “legislative intentions.”³³ Likewise, in moderate realism, the text – and not the intention of the legislator – constitutes the standard both for interpretation in the strict sense and for legal construction in interpretation.³⁴ The Girona version of moderate realism, however, differs in part from the Genoa version.³⁵ In particular, it makes room for a descriptive account of interpretive error.³⁶ Thus, Ferrer Beltrán,

distancing himself in certain respects from Guastini, endorses a criterion of acceptability and correctness which – much as in Eco’s account of *intentio operis* – is grounded in the convergent interpretive conventions of a community of interpreters.³⁷ This is the thesis that – with some adjustments – will be defended below.

3 Authors and readers (of the constitution): intention and error in legal interpretation

3.1 Textual identity of the constitution

- 14 Since the present inquiry is concerned with textual interpretation, the notion of a “documentary constitution” is central. By this I mean the constitution understood as a normative document with a determinate textual identity, that is, as a set of normative texts identified extensionally.³⁸ The author of a given documentary constitution is the *constituent power*. Although the theoretical notion of constituent power allows for a plurality of authors – one or more individuals collegially organized in different ways – the focus here is on the most common contemporary case: that in which a constituent assembly, composed of a certain number of individuals, enacts a normative document regulating at least the organization of public power and the government of the State,³⁹ and defining its territorial and personal scope of validity. Moreover, such a document must not only exist as a set of normative provisions but must also be capable of being enforced insofar as it is regarded as effective within a given society.⁴⁰
- 15 Parts of a documentary constitution, however, may also originate not from a strictly constituent power but from a *constituted power of reform* (the so-called *derivative constituent power*, or *constituaat dérivé*, misnamed in the sense that this power is not “constituent” at all).⁴¹ A *constituent power* in the strict sense is an authorizing (not an authorized) power, lacking a dynamic normative foundation and not subject to legal limits. A *constituted reforming power*, by contrast, is a power authorized by norms and dynamically grounded in the constitution itself; it may be a power of partial or total reform. Such a power is typically vested in a legislative body and exercised through regulated procedures (which, in the case of rigid constitutions, are reinforced). Accordingly, the author of a constitution may be a *single constituent* body, a constituent body *together* with a constituted reforming body (in cases of partial reform), or a *constituted* body alone (in cases of total reform). Whether partial or total, the author of a written constitution may therefore be either the constituent legislator or the ordinary legislator.
- 16 Hence, from a *strictly* textual and intentional point of view, constitutional interpretation is not essentially different from the interpretation of other legal enactments. Under a power of total reform, for example, the author of the constitution and the author of an ordinary statute may coincide one-to-one, so that there is no reason to presuppose a specific or differentiated authorship or intention. Moreover, there are significant overlaps between constitutional texts and ordinary legislation. Electoral laws share part of their material scope with the constitution; statutes regulating the exercise and judicial enforcement of fundamental rights also overlap materially with constitutional provisions.⁴² The same is true of legal principles⁴³: they are contained not only in constitutions but also – just to give an example – in civil and

criminal codes, and long before becoming a specifically constitutional topic, principles were already an object of extensive doctrinal discussion in private, criminal, or tax law.

- 17 It can therefore be reaffirmed that, from a strictly textual and intentional standpoint, constitutional interpretation is not a *sui generis* enterprise, nor does it raise exclusively textual problems that cannot also arise in the interpretation of ordinary statutes or other normative texts. That said, in legal systems with a rigid constitution, constitutional interpretation constrains the interpretation of infra-constitutional provisions and determines their validity: either such provisions admit of an interpretation consistent with the constitution, or they are invalid and must be set aside.⁴⁴

3.2 *Intentio auctoris* and interpretive error

- 18 Interpretive formalism – a position oriented toward *intentio auctoris* – takes it as obvious that the interpreter can be wrong, that is, that judges can err in their interpretations. On this view, an error occurs whenever a judge fails to identify or elucidate the meaning (supposedly) intended by the legislator: any form of judicial “creation” therefore counts as an error, precisely because the judge is not authorized by law to produce it, and to do so would amount to legislating.⁴⁵ On Ekins’s intentionalist proposal, in particular, the role assigned to constitutional interpretation is, broadly speaking, the same as the role that conversational interpretation plays in ordinary intersubjective communication.⁴⁶ Constitutional interpretation is thus conceived as an “act of knowledge” that binds the *intentio lectoris* to the *intentio auctoris*. As Ekins puts it:

[O]ne might say that interpretation should be understood in relation to some particular type of intelligible human action and is an attempt to understand that action ... [T]he Constitution does not invest judges with authority to do whatever some lawyers have been willing to label as interpretation. Strictly speaking the judicial power is not a power to interpret the law: it is a power to adjudicate disputes in accordance with law, which requires the judge, like every other subject of the law, to discern what the existing law is.⁴⁷

- 19 Ekins argues that the constitution – like any other normative act – is an object that requires understanding: “[The Constitution] is a deliberate law-making act, which falls to be understood by recognizing an intended meaning that articulates authoritative choices.”⁴⁸ This position appears to treat statutory legislation as the only *formal source* of law. As Alchourrón points out, on such a theory there is no room for regarding judicial decisions as an additional formal source of law: if a decision is solely derived from legislation, it adds nothing to the law; if it is not, then – on this view – the judge has failed to discharge the duty to apply the law without modifying it.⁴⁹
- 20 On this view, legal interpretation is tied to the *intention of the legislator*, that is, to *intentio auctoris*. Interpretation would accordingly concern the intention of a legislative body (constituent or ordinary) composed of a plurality of individuals at a given historical moment. That intention is taken to constitute the standard for “correct interpretation” of a normative text. As Raz argues, this position rests on an important hypothesis about the rationality of the system: the justification – real or supposed – for entrusting legislative powers to certain institutions makes no sense unless the laws made by those institutions are the laws they intend to make.⁵⁰ What is at stake,

therefore, is a hypothesis of instrumental rationality that presupposes a collaborative (communicative) enterprise.⁵¹

3.3 *Intentio lectoris* and interpretive error

- 21 On the view discussed above, a theory oriented toward *intentio lectoris* is associated with the interpreter's freedom in assigning meaning to a text. Here, the problem of the author in (constitutional) interpretation recedes into the background or disappears altogether. Accordingly, the very possibility of interpretive error also disappears. On this view, to interpret is to *create meaning*. At the extreme end of the spectrum, Hart likens this view to a "nightmare": "the Nightmare view that, in spite of pretensions to the contrary, judges make the law which they apply to litigants and are not impartial, objective declarers of existing law."⁵² On this radical skeptical view, every exercise of judicial interpretation is genuinely *creative of meaning*. Ultimately, the (final) interpreter of a (normative) text becomes a paradigmatic illustration of the famous conversation that Alice and Humpty Dumpty have in *Through the Looking-Glass*.⁵³
- 22 In a recent work, Campos Zamora explicitly adopts a Barthesian perspective. Drawing on the notion of *la mort de l'auteur*,⁵⁴ he argues that "reading is a creative activity that does not receive a prior meaning, but rather produces meaning by itself ... The meaning of the text cannot be anything, but what the reader himself decides to choose."⁵⁵ It is not difficult to see the parallel between this way of framing the issue and the position here attributed to radical skepticism in legal interpretation. Campos Zamora takes the Barthesian thesis as his point of departure and applies it to constitutional interpretation: *Who killed the lawmaker?*, he asks in reference to the author of the constitution (*la mort de l'auteur de la constitution*, so to speak).⁵⁶ In his role as author, he says, the (constituent) legislator becomes irrelevant once the normative texts are enacted:⁵⁷ "there has been a revolution whereby the guardian of the Constitution has ended up becoming the new lord over the constitution ..., the law becomes what the competent higher courts declare as current law."⁵⁸

3.4 *Intentio operis* and interpretive error

- 23 A text-oriented approach (*intentio operis*) starts from the premise that a text is the product of an act of *will* (that of its author) and is open to *voluntary* interpretation by others (its readers). The author produces the text and – by hypothesis – may have assigned to it one or more intended meanings; yet the text itself can "say" – and it is argued that it often does "say" – things which the author did not intend, or which go beyond what belongs to the *intentio auctoris*. This approach thus considers all three variables: author, text, and readers. An *author* may – hypothetically – associate a certain meaning with a *text*, and a *reader* may in turn be free to attribute a meaning to it. This, however, does not imply that all interpretations are equally "acceptable" or "correct," nor that only the author can determine the meaning of the text. The standard of acceptability is neither the (supposed) intention of the author nor the sole will of the interpreter but the text itself and its range of admissible readings within a given interpretive community at a given time and place. This is what *intentio operis* designates: the idea that the text incorporates a metaphorical intention that constrains

the possibilities of meaning-attribution and thereby grounds a conventional notion of interpretive error.⁵⁹

- 24 However, in the context of legal interpretation, Chiassoni treats theories oriented toward *intentio auctoris* and *intentio lectoris* as two different forms of formalism:⁶⁰ in both cases, the aim would be to identify the “true” intention of the legislator or the “true” intention of the law. If that were so, Chiassoni’s claim would raise no difficulty. There are, however, good reasons not to regard both positions as necessarily formalist. This is so because, under the first *intentio*, the relationship between the interpreter and the author of the text can be understood as a “conversational relationship” in which the author’s intention itself determines the correctness of the interpretation, and any interpretation falling beyond these bounds counts as erroneous. In the case of the *intentio operis*, on the other hand, this can be said to correspond to a formalist conception only if it is argued that the interpreter’s task is necessarily to seek the univocity of the “objective” meaning hypothetically incorporated in the text – an identification that cannot, in any event, be reduced to conversational interpretation.⁶¹ So understood, this would amount to a theory oriented towards an (ideal) reader who is searching for the supposedly objective meaning of a text;⁶² in the sense that the reader’s freedom does not exclude the possibility of its being used to search for univocity. In the field of general textual interpretation, Eco says:

The privilege conferred on the reader’s intention does not always guarantee an infinity of readings. If the reader’s intention is privileged, one must also anticipate a reader who decides to read a text in an absolutely univocal way, and who goes in search, perhaps infinitely, of this univocity.⁶³

- 25 In legal terms, a reader can adopt a formalist attitude without the theory of interpretation necessarily having to be so. As a matter of fact, a theory oriented toward *intentio operis* need not pursue objectivity in the sense characteristic of a theory oriented toward *intentio auctoris*, precisely because texts generally admit of multiple and different interpretations, independently of the “will of the author,” assuming such a will exists in the first place or is otherwise determinable. A theory oriented toward *intentio operis* does not aim to establish a single “true” meaning. Rather, it is limited to the claim that, in most cases – and perhaps in all cases, under appropriate conditions – there are some possible meanings that can be “traced” or “constructed” based on the text. Only on this basis does the theory allow us to say that some interpretations are “unacceptable,” “incorrect,” or even “delusional.”⁶⁴
- 26 Eco’s community does not operate on the basis of a code of rules dictated by a “textual legislator.” That, however, is not required, since Eco starts from criteria of common sense.⁶⁵ On his view, even adopting such minimal criteria entails accepting the inadmissibility of some “manifestly incorrect” interpretations, including – most specially – *delusional* ones. Consider, by way of a literary example, the claim that in Canto V of the *Inferno*, the *Divine Comedy* speaks – albeit in a cryptic and coded way – about the implications of the theory of general relativity. *This would be the interpretation of a madman*, a delusional interpretation. If an interpretive community were unable to exclude at least such cases, it would be a community largely made up of irrational individuals, and any hypothesis of minimal rationality would have to be abandoned. A theory of interpretation built on such a basis would itself be irrational, in addition to lacking any explanatory power.

- 27 Eco argues that the very fact that *at least one* interpretation can be excluded already implies the existence of error in textual interpretation in community-relative terms – in the sense that an interpretation can be identified as erroneous by a community of interpreters operating under a minimal rationality assumption, at a given time and place. As Eco writes: “In the terms of Popper’s theory of scientific research, this is sufficient to reject the hypothesis that interpretation lacks public criteria.”⁶⁶ If public criteria in this Popperian sense are admitted, then, with respect to the description of the interpretive practices of a given community – namely, its convergent interpretive criteria – such a reading must count as an interpretive error.
- 28 In the case of the so-called eclectic, mixed, or intermediate theory of legal interpretation, the possibility of error is not in dispute. It is taken to be obvious that interpreters can be wrong, at least in certain scenarios. Even where a decision is rendered by a “final” authority, such as a constitutional court, a distinction can still be drawn between finality and infallibility. The situation is analogous to that of a game governed by predetermined rules and overseen by a referee charged with applying them. What counts as a valid goal in soccer, for instance? Is this wholly dependent – or can it be independent – of the referee’s decision in a particular match? This, for example, is clear in H.L.A. Hart’s theory.⁶⁷
- 29 The case of moderate skepticism, however, is more complex. Guastini argues that there is no conceptual space for speaking of “error in legal interpretation”. From a *descriptive* point of view, there are only interpretations in the strict sense and interpretive constructions (respectively, within and outside a framework of usual meanings).⁶⁸ From an *evaluative* point of view, there are acceptable and unacceptable interpretations.⁶⁹ One may also say “correct” and “incorrect,” but only in an evaluative sense; such statements therefore lack truth-value. Guastini nonetheless insists on the obvious distinction between finality and infallibility. Confusing them, he says, would be like confusing strawberries and elephants⁷⁰.
- 30 Ferrer Beltrán, for his part, argues that moderate skepticism, understood as part of a moderate realist theory, is compatible with the possibility of judicial error. He maintains that the thesis of radical realism (“the law is what judges say it is”) is genuinely radical only if it is taken to mean that “the law is what each judge says the law is” – a view clearly oriented toward *intentio lectoris*, in the terms of this paper. Moderate realism, by contrast, can understand this thesis as referring not to judges considered individually but to the convergent interpretive practices of a community, practices shaped by these judges’ interaction with a set of texts – a view clearly oriented toward *intentio operis*, in the terms of this paper. To illustrate this claim, Ferrer Beltrán appeals to an analogy with the rules of soccer, and in particular to Maradona’s famous handball goal in the 1986 World Cup:
- The rules of soccer are the result of convergent interpretive practices among referees with respect to the provisions of the Laws of the Game. If it is accepted that the language – and therefore the meaning – of those provisions is conventional, then it is plausible to argue that their meaning, that is, the rules of soccer, is the product of the interpretive conventions of the relevant community ... The referee’s decision does not fall within any convergent interpretive practice concerning the provision that establishes when a valid goal is scored in a soccer match.⁷¹
- 31 There is, at this point, a clear convergence with Eco’s theory of textual interpretation. Eco insists that even in the absence of definitive criteria of “correct interpretation,” we still have criteria for identifying certain “untenable” interpretations – interpretations

that can be described as “incorrect,” in some cases even “delusional.” But what are these criteria, and who is to apply them? For it is obvious that this is like saying that we have some weak criterion of correctness (by ruling out incorrect interpretations). Eco appeals, in this regard, to criteria of common sense and interpretive economy, making it at least possible for delusional interpretations to be excluded. Ultimately, however, he suggests that it is up to a *community of interpreters* – what he calls a “community consensus”⁷² – to classify certain interpretations, if not as necessarily correct, at least as manifestly incorrect. This shows that, even in matters of interpretation, we operate with public criteria of (in)correctness in a Popperian sense. This position is grounded in a view oriented toward the work itself, toward the text understood as a chain of statements that constrains and circumscribes the possibilities of completely free interpretation. Without such constraints, the text would be fundamentally irrelevant: it would not matter whether it was one text or another.⁷³

- 32 That said, there is no denying that, in *purely alethic* terms, it is possible to ascribe any meaning – even a delusional one – to any text, thereby rendering it irrelevant whether the text is one or another. The claim advanced here is only that, given a particular text, within a *community* of interpreters, the possibilities of meaning-attribution necessarily exclude certain meanings, first and foremost those regarded as delusional. Chiassoni, who is also a moderate realist in Guastini’s sense, accepts this point, albeit with reservations: “a conformist choice, imposed by circumstances, is nevertheless always a choice.”⁷⁴ This captures the irreducible volitional component of judicial interpretation.⁷⁵ It does not, however, rule out the Gerundian position. In particular, while the problem of correctness in Guastini’s sense does exist, it cannot be the object of descriptive discourse; by contrast, on Ferrer Beltrán’s view, it can be – insofar as the convergent interpretations attached to statements of (in)correctness are themselves describable and therefore amenable to analysis in terms of truth-value (relative to a given community, at a given time and place).⁷⁶ These arguments will be expanded on below.

4 Three intentions (and three questions) in legal interpretation

4.1 *Intentio auctoris* and law: which author?

- 33 As early as 1950, Bobbio argued that the interpretation of normative texts enacted by the legislator does not – and cannot – consist in discovering the will or intention of the legislator but rather consists in *analyzing language*. Even when arguments of legislative intention are invoked, all that is achieved – on Bobbio’s view – is an expansion of the linguistic framework within which the meaning of the law is analyzed. In short, interpretation remains a matter of working with statements: transforming some into others within a process of meaning-attribution.⁷⁷
- 34 A year earlier, in 1949, Kelsen had already put his name to⁷⁸ a short prefatory essay titled *On Interpretation*⁷⁹. Here he argues that it is highly doubtful whether there exists any precise object that can be identified as “the intention of the legislator”. Although it is often assumed that the “true meaning” of a provision is the one that corresponds to the determination of such a “will”, Kelsen maintains that no such operation seems possible, “especially where the law is the result of complex procedures involving many

individuals.”⁸⁰ The intentions of one or more participants in the drafting and enactment of a legal text (as in the case of a constitution) do not coincide – according to Kelsen – with the intention of the legislator, which would have to be conceived as an elusive organic will, the so-called “will of the legislator.”⁸¹

- 35 The author or authors of a normative text – authors in the strict sense, that is, those who actually draft it – may vary for various reasons, depending, for example, on who has the power to initiate the drafting of a normative act, on the involvement of aides and advisors who collaborate in preparing bills, or on consultancies commissioned to produce draft texts. These actors often differ from those who formally possess legislative power.⁸² In the case of a constituent power, which by definition lacks a dynamic normative foundation, and also lacks rules governing legislative initiative, the picture is only partly different. In the drafting of a constitution – at least in many contemporary experiences – a wide range of actors participate, beyond those formally entrusted with adopting the text. That includes advisors, consultants, and, in some cases, participants in so-called “inclusive processes”, involving social groups, unrepresented political parties, and individuals or movements of various orientations.⁸³ In such contexts, authorship in the strict sense – the writing of the text – cannot be easily localized. Moreover, the intentions of the various individuals who have taken part in the actual formation of a normative text, even if they exist and could be reconstructed, cannot plausibly be what is meant by those who appeal to the “intention of the (constituent) legislator.”
- 36 The formation of a legislative majority of a given kind is the product of multiple interactions among legislators. From a game theory perspective, it results from a series of (iterated) cooperative games in which legislators seek support for the creation, modification, or repeal of particular provisions.⁸⁴ Many of these endorsements – the formation of alliances and coalitions – do not take place under conditions of full individual freedom. Legislators commonly follow party discipline, vote as blocs, and often do so “without adequate knowledge of the text.”⁸⁵ Moreover, although these individuals jointly contribute to the production of the same text, their linguistic competence and technical expertise inevitably differ, which makes it difficult to claim that they all intend to express the same meanings through the same statements⁸⁶. Added to this is the fact that, in many cases, the agreement required to approve a text is achieved precisely by avoiding discussion of certain detailed issues. The resulting compromise is therefore often embodied in generic formulas, which make it difficult, if not impossible, to identify any precise shared intention.⁸⁷
- 37 A further difficulty arises from the construction of so-called “counterfactual intentions”⁸⁸ in cases not expressly regulated, but in which a *legislative intention* is nevertheless presumed.⁸⁹ Suppose, for example, that “the legislator” enacts a provision which, interpreted literally, confers the right to vote on citizens. How, then, has it regulated the complementary class of non-citizens?⁹⁰ In such cases, interpreters and legal authorities often attribute a supposed “legislative intention”, even where no such intention has been plausibly expressed. The same is true of cases that – although falling, at least hypothetically, within the scope of a factual hypothesis – could not have been foreseen by “the legislator” for purely temporal reasons. This is the situation, for instance, in *Brown v. EMA* (2011)⁹¹, which concerns the protection of video games as a form of expression under the First Amendment – an issue unimaginable to the original drafters of the U.S. Constitution.

- 38 Claiming that legal interpretation consists in *ascertaining* the intention of the legislator – not merely as an argumentative device for ascribing meaning to a provision, but as the genuine objective of interpretation – obscures a fundamental difference between legal interpretation and ordinary conversational communication.⁹² In ordinary communication, it is often assumed that the primary aim is for the recipient to grasp the speaker’s communicative intention, even though the process is more complex than this picture suggests: “In ordinary communication, we proceed by trial and error.”⁹³ Under appropriate circumstances, speakers can clarify their intentions, reformulate their utterances, and correct misunderstandings in order to convey a specific meaning. In law, however, no such relationship exists.⁹⁴ There is no ongoing exchange between speaker and hearer, but rather a significant temporal gap between the intended sender and the interpreter – sometimes spanning decades or even centuries.⁹⁵ The legislator’s precise intention, assuming it exists, is therefore elusive. Interpretation conceived as a process of communicative understanding between sender and receiver, between author and reader, simply cannot take place.⁹⁶
- 39 Furthermore, theories in social ontology concerning “collective intention” do not sit well with formalism or its variants in legal interpretation.⁹⁷ At most, what remains is a turn to so-called “fictionalism,” according to which the “intention of the legislator” is a mere fiction, consisting in treating a normative text as if it had been issued by a “generic author.”⁹⁸ On closer inspection, however, nothing of formalism truly survives under these conditions. The idea of a generic author fits equally well – and indeed better – with the notion of a metaphorical (or fictitious) intention of the text itself. For this reason, this idea is more plausibly reconstructed, and better defended, in terms of *intentio operis*.⁹⁹

4.2 *Intentio lectoris* and law: which judge?

- 40 Under a theory oriented toward *intentio lectoris*, interpretation drifts along with the freedom of interpreters. On this approach, interpreters act – or may act – on the basis of their own intentions or interpretive interests, and there is no conceptual space for claiming that textual interpretation can be mistaken.¹⁰⁰ The underlying idea is that all interpretation is creative of meaning: there are no pre-established meanings, and all meaning depends on the particular attributions made by interpreters.¹⁰¹ In a way, this is how radical skepticism approaches – in a Humpty Dumpty way – the problem of interpretation: here, law is not a starting point but a point of arrival; law is the result of interpretation (of the *intentio lectoris*) that consists not in the knowledge of norms but in their production.¹⁰² *All law is judge-made law*, according to the aforementioned formula.
- 41 However, if this were so, we would reach the paradoxical conclusion that the “legislative discourse” is irrelevant, with the result – according to Barberis – that the normative statements of the sources would appear to express no meaning at all (a plainly counterintuitive consequence).¹⁰³ Moreover, if the thesis is taken seriously and all law is said to be produced exclusively by judges, the very category of judge becomes unintelligible, since it presupposes the existence of jurisdictional rules conferring interpretive authority. In other words, if law consists solely in what judges produce, how can the rules that attribute jurisdiction to them themselves have *legal* force? A well-known objection stresses that judges always apply pre-existing law, even if that

law is not necessarily substantive but only procedural. Viewed in this light, the radical thesis either collapses or becomes insubstantial.¹⁰⁴

42 Even if we consider the hypothesis of “courts of last resort” (such as constitutional courts in most contemporary systems), which bodies often tend to expand or reshape their own powers through mechanisms of self-attribution, it remains true that they require an initial “vital impulse” that brings them into existence and confers upon them their initial sphere of material competence. That impulse is necessarily heteronomous.¹⁰⁵ It follows that not all law can be judicial, even if it is conceded – as it should be – that there are, and inevitably will be, controversies about the scope of the powers of particular judicial bodies. Such controversies are nonetheless themselves framed in formal terms: which organ within the system is competent to decide this or that conflict over jurisdiction or authority?¹⁰⁶ The very notion of a judge therefore necessarily precedes the purported judicial creation of law. Not all law can be judge-made law.

43 On the other hand, in the legal domain the thesis of interpretive freedom is significantly weakened – if not altogether undermined – by the existence of a context for the adjudication of concrete cases. This point is far from negligible. For reasons that are, I think, obvious, in concrete cases brought before the courts, interpretive options are always constrained by a determinate range of factual possibilities.¹⁰⁷ As Barberis puts it:

The judge selects, as the meaning of the provision, the abstract rule that can be applied to the case at hand. Contrary to a widespread assumption, this does not make judicial interpretation more discretionary than doctrinal interpretation, but rather less so.¹⁰⁸

44 From a substantive point of view, moreover, a theory oriented toward *intentio lectoris* seems to miss the mark if one starts from the observation that all interpretation is necessarily tied to a text. Some justification is therefore required for the claim that a given attribution of meaning corresponds, in some sense, to the text being interpreted. Otherwise – if any text were open to any interpretation – the text itself would become largely irrelevant, yielding counterintuitive consequences at odds with ordinary common-sense criteria.¹⁰⁹

45 It is also worth noting that such a justification is not offered only to the parties to the proceedings but is embedded within a hierarchical institutional structure. Judges must be able to justify their interpretive choices before higher courts – whether acting on the merits or exercising review¹¹⁰ – and, in the case of collegial courts, before one another,¹¹¹ if the decision embodying that interpretation is to acquire binding force under the system’s rules.¹¹²

46 All of this significantly constrains the claims of a theory oriented toward *intentio lectoris* in law. It suggests that there are shared criteria for excluding certain interpretations – for treating them as incorrect, and in some cases delusional – and that these criteria are not merely evaluative but operate on the basis of shared parameters.¹¹³

4.3 *Intentio operis* and law: what community?

47 This section emphasizes that Ferrer Beltrán’s thesis is intended to provide a moderate realist response to the problem of judicial error, with clear affinities to Eco’s account of general textual interpretation. It should first be observed, however, that the example

used by Ferrer Beltrán – Maradona’s previously discussed handball goal – does not constitute a case of interpretive construction but rather a straightforward refereeing error. As Ferrer Beltrán himself explains, this is because the referee’s decision *does not fall within any of the convergent interpretive conventions* of the community of referees.

- 48 One aspect nevertheless calls for clarification. The referee’s error in this case does not appear to be in interpreting the rules but rather in assessing the facts. Just as a judge may err in evaluating the evidence and, as a result, in reconstructing the facts, the referee erred because he failed to notice that Maradona had scored the goal with his hand rather than with his head. The referee’s reasoning does not seem to have been something like “a goal scored with the hand (under circumstances x) counts as a valid goal.” Rather, it seems that he simply misdescribed what had happened: “that was a header,” when in fact it was a handball. In this sense, the possibility of judicial error appears obvious to me.¹¹⁴ All this notwithstanding, the textual implications of Ferrer Beltrán’s proposal remain significant, especially insofar as a parallel can be drawn, as I have argued, between his position and Eco’s account of *intentio operis*: both appeal to a community of interpreters, both are explicitly conventionalist, and both aim to offer a descriptive account of error in interpretation.
- 49 Furthermore, it is also possible, I think, to reconcile this view with Guastini’s, this by showing that moderate skepticism *à la génoise* does not require commitment to the thesis that there is no conceptual space for interpretive error.¹¹⁵ To begin with, Guastini himself argues that radical realism must be rejected insofar as it excludes the *prima facie* literal meaning of normative statements.¹¹⁶ Such statements, after all, can express different meanings (*intentio operis*). This, in my view, suggests that it cannot be ruled out that legal interpretation develops against the background of another practice that is itself undoubtedly conventional: the ordinary use of language (a point Ferrer Beltrán explicitly emphasizes). And this, it should be stressed, without implying that interpretation is reduced to the mere determination of ordinary meaning. Guastini’s position rather presupposes that conventional meanings arise under usual circumstances¹¹⁷ – under normal conditions in which a meaning is *prima facie* fixed.¹¹⁸
- 50 Legislators enact normative texts formulated in a natural language, and it would be odd to suppose that this practice does not pre-determine certain meanings already fixed by that language. This does not imply that, in legal interpretation, there is an “objective” meaning for every normative statement. It does imply, however, that there are meanings which, insofar as they are traceable to the “language of the legislator,” are partly determined by that discourse. Discourse as text (*intentio operis*) and the intention of the legislator (*intentio auctoris*) are not the same thing. Indeed, how else could one draw the distinction – central to Guastini’s account – between interpretation in the strict sense and interpretive construction?¹¹⁹ It follows that the judge *participates* in the creation of law: she is neither its mere enforcer nor its sole creator.¹²⁰ If radical realism – on Guastini’s own terms – misses the mark by excluding even *prima facie* literal meaning (that is, ordinary conventional meanings), would it not be equally mistaken, on the other hand, to fail to exclude at least those meanings (likewise conventional) that the interpretive community identifies as unacceptable, incorrect, or even delusional? Guastini, however, does not pursue the problem of interpretive error. He confines himself to pointing out the obvious distinction between definitiveness and infallibility, without developing the issue of fallibility beyond purely evaluative considerations.

- 51 As already suggested, there is at least one clear sense in which we can speak of judicial error in “fact-directed interpretation” – which nonetheless necessarily bears on “text-directed interpretation” – as something that can be an object of descriptive discourse. In line with Eco’s approach, however, Ferrer Beltrán’s position also makes it possible to account for error in textual interpretation, always in descriptive terms and always as a feature of a practice: the legal practice of meaning-attribution and adjudication. This practice, insofar as it is linked in the first instance to a conventional semantic dimension, also satisfies Raz’s hypothesis of instrumental rationality. In short, if the formation and enactment of a normative text is the product of a procedural and cooperative practice, and if the text itself is capable of expressing certain *prima facie* meanings while excluding others (at least those that are delusional), then the connection between the text and its interpretation emerges as a relevant fact in instrumental terms (there is no difficulty in saying that a text arises from an express agreement, even if it does not incorporate an express or necessarily knowable “legislative intention”).
- 52 Nonetheless, even if Guastini accepts the distinction between the finality and the infallibility of interpretive decisions,¹²¹ this does not alter the fact that it is individual judges who determine, in specific cases, what counts as a normative statement’s authentic meaning – in Kelsen’s sense – and that such determinations are legally valid, even when it can be argued that the judge has made an error.¹²² One might object: “But that is precisely the problem. If the judge has erred in identifying the law, how can the decision have legal force?” This, however, does not follow. Once finality is distinguished from infallibility, there is no difficulty in saying that a decision may be final and yet erroneous. Finality describes a state of affairs produced by procedural practice. Error, by contrast, may of course be the object of evaluative assessment, but there is also a further, realistic possibility: it may lie in the description of a state of affairs, namely, in the reconstruction of the convergent interpretive uses and practices of the relevant community of interpreters in relation to a given case.¹²³ In this way it becomes possible, at least synchronically, to identify some meanings as consolidated and others as excluded from practice.¹²⁴ This in turn allows us to say that – at least in a range of cases – an interpretation is incorrect in the sense that it counts as an interpretive error for that community, at a given time and place.
- 53 We would thus have a criterion independent of the mere will of the individual decision-maker at the moment of decision,¹²⁵ namely, the community of interpreters and its convergent interpretive practices. Ferrer Beltrán appears to suggest that a genuinely realist theory of legal interpretation must take the form of a descriptive theory of the practices of meaning-attribution and adjudication – a descriptive theory which cannot be understood apart from the interpretive conventions of a reference community, and which incorporates the notion of error into its very structure. On this view, a theory of interpretation would not be merely a theory of meaning but a *theory of the attribution of meaning* – of the practice that constitutes it. The Guastinian position, contrary to its own aspirations, tends instead toward a theory of meaning in the style of *intentio lectoris* – precisely the position from which it seeks to distance itself. Ferrer Beltrán’s proposal is therefore what is needed if one is to offer a genuinely descriptive – and not merely evaluative – account of error in judicial interpretation, and thus to fully justify the label of “moderate realism” as practiced in Genoa.

- 54 All of the foregoing may bring moderate skepticism closer to the intermediate theory, to be sure, but it does so without requiring any commitment to Hart's notion of the rule of recognition, and without reducing skeptical theory to a mere theory of adjudication. As Guastini notes, the intermediate theory suffers from an "obsession with particular cases,"¹²⁶ but this is precisely because it is, above all, a *theory of adjudication*. Nonetheless, it is important to recall that the problem of error in legal interpretation – as it is approached here – is necessarily linked to judicial interpretation. By contrast, the Genoese theory – following Bobbio and Tarello¹²⁷ – emphasizes the centrality of doctrinal interpretation and its performative role. But the issue addressed in this paper does not concern the delimitation of the proper field of inquiry.¹²⁸
- 55 There is, however, one aspect of Ferrer's position that still calls for further clarification: the problem of the interpretive community. Which community is relevant on this account? Which community are we talking about? This difficulty is explicitly raised by Ferrer Beltrán himself. With respect to the error involved in Maradona's goal, he notes that it is not easy to determine which community should count as the reference community: "Only the referees? Sports commentators too? And the fans as well?"¹²⁹ By extension, the same question arises with respect to judicial error. Are we referring only to judges? To legal scholars as well? Or even to society at large? It is important to emphasize that, whatever answer is given, the theoretical core of Ferrer's proposal remains intact, even if its scope were to change.
- 56 If, for instance, we assume that – since we are dealing with judicial error – the relevant community is composed of all judges, academics, or jurists, a difficulty immediately arises that has no clear parallel in the case of the rules of soccer. In modern legal systems, judges are typically specialized in the particular subject areas in which they are competent to judge, in the sense that the system's rules confer jurisdictional authority on them.¹³⁰ Academics and jurists likewise tend to work in specific fields of specialization in which they are, at least presumably, competent – this time in the sense of possessing expertise concerning the subject matter itself.¹³¹
- 57 Moreover, in the specific case of constitutional interpretation, judicial specialization becomes particularly significant, especially in systems with a constitutional court, which functions as the authentic and final interpreter of constitutional texts. Such courts are not, of course, the only interpreters of the constitution – which is also interpreted by legislative and executive branches, among other authorities and organs of the State¹³² – but constitutional courts' institutional position places them above all others, at least with respect to constitutionally justiciable cases (not all cases, of course, are justiciable).¹³³ In this domain, then, the relevant community of judges would be a very limited one, coinciding with those judges who are institutionally competent to interpret the constitution in the authentic – and ultimate – sense. At this point, preserving the relevance of Ferrer's position seems to require reconceiving the notion of community. One might refer, for example, to a community of constitutional lawyers, to a broader community of constitutional scholars, or perhaps even – at least in certain cases and for certain semantic conventions – to society at large, insofar as it can exclude at least some interpretive possibilities, such as delusional ones.

5 With some caveats...

58 In the broader context of textual interpretation, Eco observes that a work anticipates a system of psychological, cultural, and historical expectations. Scholars studying the *Commedia*, for example, frequently debate the interpretations that should be attributed to Dante's work, considering both the text itself and the time and place in which it was written. On this basis, they tend to exclude "updated interpretations" that would conflict with those embedded in that specific historical and cultural context. Thus, in criticizing one of Dante's interpreters, Eco remarks:

Rossetti starts from the unquestioned conviction that Dante was a Freemason, a Templar, and a Rosicrucian, and assumes that the Masonic-Rosicrucian symbol is the following: a rose inscribed with a cross, beneath which appears a pelican which, according to legend, feeds its young with flesh torn from its own breast. He must then show that this symbol also appears in Dante. In doing so, he runs the risk of proving only the more reasonable hypothesis, namely that Masonic symbolism was inspired by Dante. To avoid this, one might advance the hypothesis of a third, archetypal text, which would allow Rossetti to kill two birds with one stone: he would prove both that the Masonic tradition is very ancient and that Dante was inspired by that ancient tradition. Rossetti's tragedy is that he finds no striking analogy between Dante and Masonic symbolism, and, having no analogies that could point to the archetype, he does not even know what archetype to look for.¹³⁴

59 In Eco's terms, this kind of reading falls under a *post hoc, ergo ante hoc* argument. In debates about the limits of textual interpretation, the problem of "updated meanings" becomes especially salient from the cultural and historical perspective just mentioned. An interpretation that entirely disregards such circumstances tends to be excluded and classified as erroneous, for the reasons already indicated.

60 Let me, at this point, briefly consider legal interpretation in relation to the historical, cultural, and psychological expectations that, as noted, a text generates. *Exempli gratia*: a constitutional interpretation of the kind offered by Thomas Dew, one of the ideologues of Confederate slavery,¹³⁵ was possible in its time but is impossible today; it would now be regarded as a delusional reading, entirely outside the convergent interpretive criteria governing constitutional texts on freedom and equality.¹³⁶ Other interpretations – such as that adopted in *Brown v. Board of Education* (1954)¹³⁷ – were initially viewed by many, if not most, as interpretive errors, often attributed to judicial activism. In its own day, by contrast, *Plessy v. Ferguson* (1896)¹³⁸ was not widely regarded as erroneous. Dew's position (consistent with the doctrine preceding *Plessy*), the ruling in *Plessy* itself, and the decision in *Brown* are all based on interpretations of the U.S. Constitution concerning freedom and equality: equality only among members of each "racial category" (Dew), "separate but equal" (*Plessy*), and equality in terms of equal freedom (*Brown*). Although today, decades later, the status and implications of *Brown* remain a matter of controversy, the opinion constitutes a consolidated interpretation, regarded as correct according to the standards of the relevant interpretive community on the basis of the *intentio operis*, irrespective of the historical circumstances surrounding the enactment of the Constitution.¹³⁹

61 As will be apparent from these cases, some of these readings are indeed "updated interpretations." However, in modern legal culture – particularly in constitutional interpretation – certain normative texts are taken to be capable of expressing evolving meanings in light of the changing circumstances to which they are applied,¹⁴⁰ without

this necessarily entailing a judgment of incorrectness¹⁴¹ (although the degree of permissible adaptation depends, of course, on the wording of the text). In short, under a conception of interpretation grounded not in the *intentio auctoris* but in the *intentio operis*, and situated within a particular cultural and historical environment, an interpretation that is legally correct may depart from the original historical and cultural expectations a text might be thought to have generated. It is here that a significant divergence emerges between general textual interpretation and legal interpretation.¹⁴²

62 Thus, whereas an updated interpretation of the *Commedia* – such as the one discussed by Eco – is regarded as incorrect precisely because it is an “updated” reading, the product of a *post hoc, ergo ante hoc* argument, the same is not true – or at least not necessarily true – of legal interpretation. In the legal domain, a meaning that is considered erroneous or implausible under certain circumstances may, depending on the case, cease to be so under an updated interpretation, as a result of changes in the convergent interpretive conventions governing the value of the text. This is true even with cases which could not possibly have been envisaged by the original drafters, and which are “renewed” for the purposes of a new “legal reality” (such as the aforementioned *Brown v. EMA* case concerning video games)¹⁴³, or even in scenarios in which persons are treated, by operation of law, as if a certain factual reality *had not occurred*: after the abolition of slavery, treating individuals *as if* they had never been slaves; after the fall of Nazism, treating individuals *as if* they had never lost their German citizenship (under a kind of retroactive ontology concerning such institutional facts¹⁴⁴).

63 Finally, I should stress that the theoretical value of Ferrer Beltrán’s proposal, with the adjustments indicated here, is considerable, especially for the purpose of developing a moderate realism capable of offering an acceptable and coherent response to the problem of judicial error. However, Ferrer Beltrán’s proposal does not resolve – as perhaps no proposal can resolve – what Celano calls “the paradox of nomodynamics”¹⁴⁵: the problem of authority, especially interpretive authority, constrains the possibility of correction through the finality of decisions. A final decision (such as that on Maradona’s goal, or, in our systems, a decision issued by a constitutional court) produces legal effects, is binding, and shapes the rights and obligations of individuals even if it is plausibly argued to be erroneous. This points to an irresolvable tension between the problem of finality and the problem of the correctness of legal decisions. In short, we can distinguish – even on sound conceptual and theoretical grounds – between finality and correctness. We can also draw this distinction for descriptive purposes. But this does not solve the practical problem that arises from that tension. The paradox of nomodynamics remains a *cul-de-sac* for legal theory.¹⁴⁶

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NOTES

1. In both cases, the translation of the epigraph is mine.
2. Cfr. Powell 1985.
3. E.g. Constitution of the Republic of Ecuador, art. 427; Bolivian Constitution, art. 196, II.
4. Chiassoni 2011: 163.
5. Eco 1992; Eco 2016.
6. See Eco 2016: 36 ff.; Eco 1992.
7. Eco 1992; Eco 2016.
8. Guastini (2011: 7) says: "Legal interpretation obviously belongs to the genre of textual interpretation" (my translation). Dworkin (1996), for his part, in "How Law is Like Literature", recommended that jurists study literary theory in order to better understand legal interpretation. I will not comment on the results obtained by Dworkin himself. Finally, I would like to recall that, as early as 1970, Bobbio advocated broadening the field of study of general legal theory by drawing on semiotics, among other disciplines. Bobbio (2012 [1970]: 3) argues: "[T]he general theory of law has never found itself in such favorable conditions to broaden its field and delve deeper into it: consider the help it has received and continues to receive from

rapidly developing disciplines such as general systems theory, semiotics, deontic logic, and so on” (my translation).

9. Of course, nothing rules out the hypothesis that an author may intend to express more than one meaning (or more than one rule) such that meanings (M1 and M2, and so on) are among those originally envisaged – and intended – by the author himself. This may be so even where such meanings run counter to what the “letter” of a provision would suggest. Consider, for example, the following passage from *Holy Trinity Church v. United States*, 143 U.S. 457, 459 (1892): “a thing may be within the letter of the statute and yet not within the statute, because not within its spirit, nor within the intention of its makers.” In a recent paper, Velluzzi (2024) notes, in addition to this reference, a parallel in Italian case law: “The interpretation of legal provisions ... consists in ascertaining the actual will of the legislator, even beyond the literal formulation” (Cons. Stato, 1996) (my translation).

10. In the infamous *Dred Scott* ruling, Chief Justice Taney states: “No one, we presume, supposes that any change in public opinion ... should induce the court to give to the words of the Constitution a more liberal construction in their favor than they were intended to bear when the instrument was framed and adopted ... It is not only the same in words, but the same in meaning, and delegates the same powers to the Government, and reserves and secures the same rights and privileges to the citizen; and as long as it continues to exist in its present form, it speaks not only in the same words, but with the same meaning and intent with which it spoke when it came from the hands of its framers.” [*Dred Scott v. Sandford*, 60 U.S. 393, 426 (1857)].

11. See Alexander & Sherwin 2008: 131 ff.

12. I am referring to what is known as “interpretive formalism”; that is, the conception according to which the judge only has the power to “declare the law in force,” insofar as the judge must be solely “the voice of the legislator” (see Bobbio 2011: 77 ff., my translation).

13. On the other hand, it can also be argued that some contemporary natural law theories of interpretation amount to a version – albeit a radical one – of “formalism,” understood as a theory of interpretation oriented toward the *intentio auctoris* – and in fact oriented toward a fictitious author, namely, Reason. Massini Correias (2010), in a study on interpretation, maintains that natural law theory can be characterized as a theory that defends the thesis of “rational sources” (as opposed to the thesis of “social sources”). On this view, the ultimate task of interpretation would be to identify the “legal requirements” of such “rational sources” – that is, the requirements or norms of “rational law,” allegedly self-evident insofar as they derive from “basic human goods.” Interpretation would thus consist in “interpreting” the provisions of a fictitious legislator rather than those of a flesh-and-blood one: as Bobbio (1985) put it, it would be a matter of identifying the norms of a hypothetical “legislative reason,” to which “creative power has been attributed” (hence the idea of “rational sources”). But this is not all. This position is also tied to the alleged existence of a specific substantive rationality on the part of the addressees of the “commands of reason.” In short, it would be necessary to assume the existence of a rational law whose subjects, in turn, are fully rational: capable of grasping certain (legal) rules of justice and injustice and of acting accordingly. Needless to say, such a hypothesis is not historically verifiable.

14. Bobbio (1971) said that “no one seriously holds this position anymore” (my translation). As we shall see, things do not seem to be exactly that way. Although under different labels, various versions of “formalism” continue to haunt the debate.

15. This is the case, for instance, with some theses of “classical originalism,” referring precisely to the interpretation of the Constitution understood as reconstructing the intention of the Founding Fathers (see Sardo 2018: 33 ff.).

16. Ekins 2017: 1.

17. See, *inter alia*, Bobbio 1964; Guastini 2016a: 157 ff.; Ferrajoli 2011: 97 ff.; Baquerizo 2021.

18. See section 3.1.

19. For a critical response to Ekins's proposal, see Canale & Poggi 2019. For a discussion with partly different aims, see Brunet & Poggi 2024; and Goldsworthy 2024.
20. Eco 2016: 40.
21. Eco 1990: 2.
22. See Campos Zamora 2022: 271.
23. See Guastini 2012.
24. See, for example, Troper 2020.
25. Gray 1997 [1921].
26. Guastini 2011: 425 (my translation).
27. Eco 2016: 155.
28. Eco 1992: 63 ff.
29. Eco 2016: 25. In this position, the same text could express different meanings to different readers; meanings that could otherwise be contradictory, or give rise to varied combinations that would nevertheless be acceptable provided they could be proven to be minimally plausible within a community of interpreters.
30. See Chiassoni 2011.
31. See Hart 1961: chap. VII; Bulygin 1992; Comanducci 2011.
32. Barberis 2015: 238. Sandro (2022: 108 ff.), for his part, suggests that Guastini is (partially) moving toward a position influenced by Hart (we should assume that, like Molière's bourgeois gentleman, the Genoese are quasi-Hartians without knowing it). Sandro also argues that there can be no genuine "moderate skepticism." I do not find this position persuasive. A residual form of radical skepticism in Guastini's theory lies in his refusal to admit error in legal interpretation and to treat interpretive discourse in descriptive terms. As should be clear from this paper, these are precisely the theses that, in my view, Genoese-style moderate realism must abandon. Nor do I see any good reason to abandon the label "realism" or "moderate skepticism." Rejecting the radical thesis amounts precisely to distancing oneself from the pretensions of the "radical wing" of realism – and especially from the idea that there are no meanings prior to interpretation. And this is, in fact, a thesis that Guastini himself rejects. Why, then, should he not be regarded as a moderate?
33. See Hart 1961: chap. VII.
34. In the former case, the interpreter chooses a meaning within a framework of plausible meanings of the normative text; in the latter, he chooses a creative meaning that cannot be traced within that framework. See Guastini 2015. See also Barberis 2011a; Barberis 2015a; Barberis 2015b. In a partly different sense, see Solum 2010.
35. With its Bobbian, Rossian, and Kelsenian influence. See, *inter alia*, Ferrer Beltrán & Ratti 2011; Guastini 1999; Bobbio 1950; Ross 2009 [1968]; Kelsen 2000 [1950].
36. Ferrer Beltrán 2012.
37. Eco 2016.
38. See, *inter alia*, Barberis 2006: chap. IV; Maldonado Muñoz 2020.
39. This is the formal (not axiological) concept of constitution: see Maldonado Muñoz 2020.
40. Bobbio 1964; Guastini 2005; Guastini 2016a: 157 ff.
41. See Baquerizo 2024.
42. See Guastini 2016b: 263.
43. Although the category itself is controversial: see, *inter alia*, Ratti 2023; Comanducci 1998.
44. Whether a provision "admits of" a constitution-conforming interpretation is itself a matter of controversy, particularly when it comes to assessing the material conformity of infra-constitutional provisions (see Bobbio 1971).
45. See, *inter alia*, Bobbio 1971; Bulygin 2003.
46. For an effective refutation of this thesis, see Poggi 2020.
47. Ekins 2017: 16.

48. Ekins 2017: 19.
49. Alchourrón 2010: 160.
50. See Raz 2009: 274.
51. See Marquisio Aguirre 2024.
52. Hart 1977: 973.
53. As is well known, on hearing from Humpty Dumpty that when he uses a word it means just what he chooses it to mean, Alice asks him whether it is in fact possible to make words mean many different things. Humpty Dumpty replies that what matters here is not what words mean but simply who is in charge: “The question,” said Humpty Dumpty, “is which is to be master – that’s all.” Guastini (2012: 50) says: “The nightmare theory ... is a radical form of skepticism. According to this theory, *anything goes* in matters of interpretation, and this is so for a Humpty-Dumpty-type reason.” On this example, see Scarpelli 1971.
54. Barthes 1977 [1967].
55. Campos Zamora 2022: 275.
56. Today, the problem presents further dimensions, especially in relation to the development of generative artificial intelligence: e.g., Rábanos & Spaić 2025; Misseri 2023.
57. Campos Zamora 2022: 283. However, it should be clarified that Campos Zamora refers particularly to the German case. Otherwise, Campos Zamora’s position seems to be not only descriptive but also critical.
58. Campos Zamora 2022: 286.
59. See Eco 2016.
60. Chiassoni 2011: 161.
61. This is a meaning that, on closer inspection, does not coincide with that of the *intentio auctoris*. If that were the case, the distinction introduced above would no longer have any reason to exist.
62. In the legal sphere, this idea can be related – at least indirectly – to the position an interpreter might adopt with respect to what some originalists call “public original meaning.” See Fallon (2021): “Public meaning originalists do not all agree about everything, but they coalesce around a central tenet: the original and unchanging meaning of a constitutional provision is either (1) what a reasonable person who knew the publicly available facts about the context of its drafting would have taken it to mean or (2) what literate and informed members of the public actually understood it to be at the time of its promulgation.” It is also true, however, that there are other – hypothetically more demanding – ways of pursuing interpretive uniqueness, as in the case of the so-called “Judge Hercules” (see Dworkin 1986; cf. Aarnio 2012).
63. Eco 2016: 38 (my translation). Here, I am using the Italian version. The English version is slightly different: “To privilege the initiative of the reader does not necessarily mean to guarantee the infinity of readings. If one privileges the initiative of the reader, one must also consider the possibility of an active reader who decides to read a text univocally.” (Eco, 1990, 51).
64. Eco maintains that even the most radical deconstructionists must accept that texts cannot mean just anything without limit (Eco 2016: 24). Among other examples, he offers a purely imaginary one in which Jack the Ripper claims to have committed his crimes on the basis of a series of instructions drawn from the Gospels (Eco 2016: 76). In this case, “the Ripper” is a reader like any other, but his reading is “delusional,” the interpretation of a “madman” (on delusional beliefs, see, in any case, Bortolotti & Zambra 2025). It is interesting to note that, within general legal theory, the notion of “madness” has also been employed by Jori. In his book *Del diritto inesistente* (Jori 2010), he makes use of the concept of madness through the example of the so-called “madman of Pavia,” a man who “made trains depart” without being a “real” railway official (*capostazione*). Common sense, Jori argues, serves to identify the “law” of the “madman of Pavia” as a case of “non-existent law” (*ibid.*).
65. Just as Jori does in the book mentioned in the previous note.

66. Eco 1992: 25. Although Popper did not deal with law – and even less with legal interpretation – it nonetheless bears recalling that in *Conjectures and Refutations* (Popper 2002) he notes a shift in the ordinary understanding of the expression “the judge must interpret the law.” Whereas today it is generally assumed that judges enjoy a certain margin of interpretation, and may even identify different plausible meanings traceable to the text, in the past, Popper observes, the same expression was commonly used to claim that judges ought to interpret the law as conceived by the legislator – that is, in the only sense regarded as “correct.”
67. See Hart 1961: chap. VII.3.
68. I refer again to Guastini 2015.
69. Guastini 2015.
70. See Guastini 2013; Arena 2018.
71. Ferrer Beltrán 2012: 263 (my translation).
72. See Eco 1992: chap. 7; Eco 2016: chap. 4-4.6.
73. This would also be a way of approaching the problem that could be considered contrary to common sense and minimum criteria of rationality.
74. Chiassoni 2011: 163 (my translation).
75. Guastini 2011: 27 ff.
76. Ferrer Beltrán 2012: 273.
77. Bobbio 1950. On Bobbio’s position on interpretation, see Maldonado Muñoz 2024a.
78. Núñez Vaquero 2011.
79. Kelsen 2000 [1950].
80. Kelsen 2000 [1950]: xiv.
81. Kelsen 2000 [1950]: xiv.
82. Kelsen 2000 [1950]: xiv.
83. Ebrahim & Miller 2010.
84. Maldonado Muñoz 2021: 97 ff.
85. Kelsen 2000 [1950].
86. Kristan 2017: 94 ff.
87. See Bobbio 1971; Marmor, 2009; Celano, 2017: 29.
88. Celano 2017: 33.
89. See Baum Levenbook 2024.
90. See Poggi 2007: 623. See also the decisions on same sex marriage in the Ecuadorian case. In these, in the majority votes and in the dissenting votes, two versions of the argument *a contrario* were used (in this regard, see Maldonado Muñoz 2024b).
91. *Brown v. Entertainment Merchants Assn.*, 564 U.S. 786 (2011).
92. See Poggi 2020.
93. Celano 2017: 21 (my translation).
94. Celano 2017: 33.
95. It is not possible to reproduce the conditions of ordinary communication, nor is it (always) possible, as we have seen, to point to a precise and identifiable sender to whom a communicative intention can be attributed. The “(constituent) legislator” is, in reality, a group of individuals whose interests, values, knowledge, and opinions differ among themselves.
96. In this regard, Chiassoni (2019: 241 ff.) states: “The relationship between judges and legislators is a ‘conversation’ with a subject – the legislator – who is not in a position to respond, at least not immediately. New provisions are therefore required ... And these provisions, in turn, must themselves be interpreted, and their legal effects often depend on a variety of factors, including, for example, the principle of non-retroactivity. This suggests that the relationship between judges and legislators is a game that judges play with the texts of legal provisions...” (my translation).
97. Canale 2022.

98. Cf. Doerfler 2017; Canale 2022.
99. In addition to the above, see section 4.3.
100. Also in accordance with the image of the “Frankification of Legal Realism” discussed by Leiter 1997.
101. See Troper 2020.
102. See Tarello 1980.
103. See Barberis 2011b: 206; Barberis 2015a: 232.
104. In controversy with J.C. Gray, Kelsen (2006 [1949]: 152) argues: “The court always applies preexisting law, but the law it applies may not be substantive, but adjective law. The court may apply only those general norms which determine its own existence and procedure, the general norms which confer upon certain individuals the legal capacity to act as a court of a certain State.”
105. In Hartian terms, “the existence of a court entails the existence of secondary rules conferring jurisdiction on a changing succession of individuals and so making their decisions authoritative” (Hart 1961: 136).
106. Celano 2002.
107. See Taruffo 2010: 268 ff.
108. Barberis 2015: 233 (my translation).
109. See Jori 2010.
110. This also holds as an intra-procedural reasoning mechanism, with regard to both the function it performs vis-à-vis the parties and the function it performs vis-à-vis appellate judges (see Ferrer Beltrán 2021: 189 ff.).
111. This is a process in which, under the rule of law, judges (and other officials) interact with one another in accordance with a set of conventions that define the limits of what, in interpretive terms, they are willing to propose within a given practice. Ira K. Lindsay (2021) characterizes it as a practice in which what she calls “horizontal trust” applies (at least among judges of the same “level”). See also Posner (2010: 206), who more generally argues that “their freedom of action is also hampered by the need to compromise with other judges who may be less adventurous than they, in order to command a majority.” In an even more general sense, on the formation of conventions, see the classic work by Lewis (2002 [1969]).
112. Maldonado Muñoz 2021: 104 ff.
113. Even taking into account that the notions of “madness” and “sanity” are also based on conventional criteria of common sense and public community criteria. See Jori 2010: 13 ff.
114. But compare Dei Vecchi 2023.
115. I do not mean to suggest that Guastini would agree with me on this point. If this were the case, the *intentio auctoris* and the *intentio lectoris* that would separate us could only be saved by resorting to the *intentio operis*. And yet, navigating this territory is like walking on a rough road. Consequently, *lasciate ogne speranza, voi ch'intrate*.
116. Guastini 2011: 425.
117. See Wittgenstein 2009 [1953]: 61 ff. (§ 142).
118. With the necessary clarifications regarding the impossibility of a literal meaning outside of context (see Poggi 2007).
119. See Canale 2019.
120. See Barberis 2015.
121. Guastini 2013: 116.
122. This leads to the so-called “paradox of nomodynamics” (see Celano 2019: 67 ff).
123. See Ferrer Beltán 2012.
124. Cf. Tobia & Mikhail 2021.
125. Ferrer Beltrán 2012: 266.
126. Guastini 2014: 232.

127. Bobbio 1950; Tarello 1974.

128. All in all, it can be said that, with regard to doctrinal interpretation, the problem of error is no different from that which arises in general textual interpretation. Curiously, a possible answer to this problem was already found in Bobbio's literature. According to him, jurists frequently disagree on the meaning of different provisions, and would do so without limit if a set of conventions did not apply among them (see Bobbio 1954).

129. Ferrer Beltrán 2012: 263.

130. See, *inter alia*, Calzetta 2025: 149 ff. (also including a sophisticated treatment of rules of competence, or power-conferring rules).

131. Here, *competence* is used as the ability to use a means to achieve a specific end, making this always a “relative statement” (see Wittgenstein 2014 [1929]: 45).

132. See Troper 2006.

133. See Guastini 2012.

134. Eco 2016: 106 (my translation).

135. See Dew 1832.

136. Obviously, I am not using the terms *possible-impossible* in an alethic sense here. The mere alethic possibility of ascribing any meaning to any text is always present; except, of course, that this is not a genuine problem for discussion.

137. *Brown v. Board of Education of Topeka*, 347 U.S. 483 (1954).

138. *Plessy v. Ferguson*, 163 U.S. 537 (1896).

139. See Waldstreicher 2009.

140. Pragmatically – Haack (2020: 107) argues – this is a way in which the system adapts by trying to meet the needs and demands of a changing society.

141. Under the hypothesis, for example, of the “living constitution.”

142. A theory of interpretation so conceived must be able to explain the *evolving interpretive practices* of a given interpretive community. Scavuzzo's (2025) proposal, for example, moves in this direction.

143. Bix 2012: 153.

144. See Tuzet 2019; Celano 2019.

145. Celano 2019: 67.

146. A more detailed explanation of the paradox cannot be addressed in these pages. In any case, I refer to Celano 2002; Celano 2017; Celano 2019.

ABSTRACTS

This essay analyzes three “intentions” that operate in theories of textual interpretation: *intentio auctoris* (author's intention), *intentio lectoris* (reader's intention), and *intentio operis* (intention of the work). These categories are then transferred to the analysis of legal interpretation. In particular, it discusses the notion of “intention of the (constituent) legislator.” The central thesis is that, although formalist and radical skeptical positions still persist in the debate, a more fruitful path lies in a moderately realistic theory oriented toward *intentio operis*. On this approach, the text (of the constitution) imposes interpretive restrictions through a community of interpreters, thus allowing for the possibility of interpretive error – under public criteria of correction – without falling into a subjectivist conception.

Avtorji in bralci (ustave). Problem namena v pravnem razlaganju. To besedilo analizira tri »namene«, ki delujejo v teorijah besedilne razlage: *intentio auctoris* (namen avtorja), *intentio lectoris* (namen bralca) in *intentio operis* (namen dela). Te kategorije se nato prenesejo na analizo pravnega razlaganja. Posebej se obravnava pojem »namena (ustavodajnega) zakonodajalca«. Osrednja teza je, da čeprav v razpravi še vedno vztrajajo formalistična in radikalno skeptična stališča, bolj plodna pot vodi k zmerno realistični teoriji, usmerjeni k *intentio operis*. Po tem pristopu besedilo (ustave) prek skupnosti razlagalcev nalaga razlagalne omejitve, s čimer omogoča možnost razlagalne napake – po javnih merilih pravilnosti – ne da bi pri tem zapadli v subjektivistično pojmovanje.

INDEX

Keywords: legal interpretation, intention of the legislator (constituent), semiotics, intentio operis, moderate realism

motsless! Pravno razlagane, namen (ustavodajnega) zakonodajalca, semiotika, intentio operis, zmerni realizem

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